

Controlled Functionalization Strategy of Proteins Preserves their Structural Integrity While Binding to Nanocarriers

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The use of proteins as targeting agents often requires their chemical modification for their efficient attachment to a given surface. However, no control over the protein integrity and functionality has been demonstrated to date. Chemical over-modification causes the loss of the native structure of the protein and thus limits its targeting efficiency. To preserve structural integrity, a minimal modification strategy of proteins is developed while maintaining their functionality. Apolipoprotein A1 (ApoA1) and liposomes are utilized as a nanocarrier platform. Monitoring NHS ester chemistry by time-of-flight mass spectrometry experiments, the proposed functionalization route allows the effective chemical coupling of the minimally modified ApoA1 to the surface of the liposomes via a click chemistry reaction. The stability of the modified ApoA1 is ensured by analyzing the secondary structure by circular dichroism spectroscopy and the corresponding melting point by nano differential scanning fluorimetry. Furthermore, ApoA1 attachment to the liposomes is confirmed by flow cytometry experiments. The procedure presented in this study has the potential to be easily transferred to other proteins while introducing only minimally necessary chemical modifications to be covalently attached to different drug delivery platforms. This can help to improve their targeting efficiency for future biomedical applications.

However, the chemical modification of these proteins is often required to introduce new functionalities or improve stability. Traditionally, the most frequently used strategies are based on the modification of cysteine and lysine residues, since they are the most nucleophilic amino acids.^[2] In particular, the high abundance of lysine (Lys) on protein surfaces leads to the development of the functionalization of Lys residues, typically involving the reaction with electrophilic reagents such as activated esters (e.g., *N*-hydroxysuccinimide esters).^[3] Despite the widespread and well-established Lys modification methods, these strategies were developed for specific proteins, therefore limiting their application to any other, as they depend mainly on the structural particularities of each protein. Thus, new functionalization strategies need to be individually established. Furthermore, despite the current efforts on the development and use of modified proteins as targeting agents, performing

chemical modifications without compromising the proteins' native structure is still a challenge.^[4] This problem can lead to loss of protein functionalities and accordingly the efficiency of the final system.

One strategy that has been widely explored for the functionalization of macromolecules and nanoparticles in the last few years is based on click chemistry since the procedure is very efficient and can be carried out in aqueous medium.^[5] There are two different bio-orthogonal coupling approaches: copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC)^[6] and strain-promoted alkyne-azide cycloaddition (SPAAC).^[7] The second strategy is more suitable for applications requiring cell studies, since the use of copper as a catalyst is avoided, and it has already been established for functionalization of antibodies.^[8] However, since there is no site-selective modification available for proteins, a new strategy needs to be developed. A promising approach is taking advantage of the accessible amino groups from the Lys residues. As such, NHS ester chemistry, which requires mild reaction conditions, could be employed to introduce azide groups that later can intervene in a cycloaddition reaction. Although a two-step reaction would be required in this case, the use of NHS chemistry would allow this strategy to be easily transferred to any other macromolecules containing amino groups.

1. Introduction

Proteins are biological macromolecules with unique 3D structures, which provide them with specific properties and functionalities applicable to industrial and pharmaceutical applications.^[1]

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Scheme 1. Schematic step-by-step illustration of ApoA1 azidation (Step 1), DBCO conjugation on liposomal surface (Step 2), and click chemistry reaction between azidated-ApoA1 and DBCO-liposomes (Step 3).

On the other hand, apolipoproteins are known for being amphipathic macromolecules able to interact with both the lipids in the lipoprotein particles and with the aqueous environment, giving structural stability and providing specific recognition units for these lipoprotein particles.^[9] Among them, Apolipoprotein A1 (ApoA1) is the major component of high density lipoproteins (HDL).^[10] ApoA1 is an attractive protein for nanocarrier functionalization due to its specific functionalities, such as the capacity to provide the so-called stealth effect^[11] and to enable the passing of the blood-brain-barrier.^[12] Thus, the use of modified ApoA1 for subsequent attachment to different surfaces or nanocarriers could enhance their use as targeting agents. In addition, given that ApoA1 contains 23 reactive amino groups (22 lysine + N-terminus), it would be a model protein to develop a functionalization strategy via NHS ester reaction.

Despite being well known for decades, liposomes are still one of the most utilised nanocarriers due to their versatility and biocompatibility, given the similarity of the lipid bilayer to biological membranes.^[13] Additionally, the liposomal composition allows surface modifications such as the attachment of different targeting moieties or the formation of advanced complex structures.^[14] Moreover, the composition of the liposome bilayer influences functionalities such as cellular uptake^[15] and

the ability to react with specific functional moieties.^[8] Additionally, surface available amino groups are provided in liposome formulations that incorporate the lipid 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE), which in turn enables the use of NHS ester chemistry for further engineering and functionalization strategies under mild conditions.

Here, ApoA1 was used as a model protein to develop a functionalization strategy while keeping its native structure intact. Protein modification with an azide-PEG linker was carried out via NHS ester chemistry under physiological conditions. To monitor the reaction, the molecular weight of the azidated-ApoA1 was determined by time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-ToF), stability was evaluated by analyzing the secondary structure using circular dichroism spectroscopy (CD spectroscopy) and the melting/denaturation point was examined by nano differential scanning fluorimetry (nanoDSF). As such, the minimally modified ApoA1 was further used for attachment to liposomes as model nanocarrier systems. For that, a strained alkyne was coupled to liposomes again using NHS ester chemistry to promote the final bio-orthogonal copper-free click chemistry reaction (SPAAC) between the azidated protein and the alkyne-functionalized liposomes (**Scheme 1**). The effective coupling of ApoA1 to the liposomes was confirmed by flow cytometry experiments and cellular

Figure 1. Characterization of azidated ApoA1. A) MALDI-ToF spectra of unfunctionalized and functionalized ApoA1 including different azide/amino group ratios. B) Sample $N_3:NH_2$ ratios used for reaction and number of azide molecules quantified by MALDI. C) CD-spectroscopy measurements of modified ApoA1 with different azide groups per NH_2 ratios.

internalization was investigated in RAW264.7 macrophage cells. This minimal protein modification approach could be easily transferable to any other NH_2 -presenting protein, ensuring their structural stability while maintaining functionality.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. ApoA1 Azidation Via NHS Ester Reaction and Protein Stability Characterization

ApoA1 was used as a representative protein to study the influence of chemical modification on protein structural integrity. Apolipoproteins can induce the so-called stealth effect when present on nanocarrier surfaces, thereby extending blood circulation times of drug delivery systems.^[16] Additionally, apolipoproteins are of high interest for potential targeting of cells expressing scavenger receptor B1 (SR-B1),^[17] e.g. endothelial cells.^[18] Thus, conjugating apolipoproteins to nanocarriers is generally desired.

To maintain such biological activity, the apolipoproteins need to be recognizable and fully functional after coupling to a nanocarrier surface. Thus, it is of utmost importance that the applied coupling strategy retains the native structure of the protein.

In this study, NHS-chemistry was used for the azidation of ApoA1 via the ϵ -amino groups of lysine residues. This way, azide groups can be introduced into the protein, which can later participate in a click reaction. For the reaction, the ratio of azide groups per ApoA1 was adjusted between the minimum and maximum amount possible to further determine the effect of azidation on protein structure. In total, ApoA1 contains 23 reactive amino groups (22 lysine + N-terminus). The $N_3:NH_2$ ratios were tuned from 0.2:1 to 5:1. Subsequently, the number of azide groups successfully attached to the protein was characterized by mass spectrometry (MALDI-ToF). The obtained results are shown in **Figure 1**. It can be seen from the corresponding spectra in **Figure 1A**, that the mass increase is proportional to the number of azide linkers used. Depending on the desired ratio, and

Figure 2. NanoDSF measurements showing unfolding and refolding ramps of ApoA1 azidated with different $N_3:NH_2$ ratios. Upper graphs: ratio of fluorescence recorded at 350 and 330 nm, lower graphs: corresponding 1st derivatives.

taking into account that the reaction yield for the NHS coupling is $\approx 50\%$, between 1 and 23 azide groups per protein could be attached, as summarized in the table in Figure 1B. Additionally, the reactivity of the introduced azide groups was verified by coupling of a dibenzylcyclooctyne (DBCO)-PEG linker and subsequent analysis by sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and MALDI-ToF. The detected mass increases after DBCO coupling are shown in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).

Next, the stability of the modified protein was evaluated by checking the integrity of the secondary structure by CD spectroscopy measurements. The obtained spectra can be seen in Figure 1C. The spectra remained similar to the native structure at low azidation degrees ($N_3:NH_2$ 0.1:1 to 0.8:1, Figure 1C left), but changed significantly at higher degrees ($N_3:NH_2$ 1:1 to 5:1, Figure 1C right). This suggests that the secondary structure of ApoA1 was affected when a high number of functional groups was introduced.

For further evaluation of the stability of the secondary structure as a function of $N_3:NH_2$ ratios, the corresponding melting points were characterized by differential scanning fluorimetry (nanoDSF) as this not only takes the secondary but also the tertiary protein structure into account. In nanoDSF measurements, the intrinsic fluorescence of tryptophan groups is monitored dur-

ing thermal unfolding. In this way, melting points of proteins can be determined, and information is obtained complementary to CD spectroscopy. The obtained nanoDSF results can be seen in Figure 2. Here, native ApoA1 showed a melting point $\approx 60^\circ C$ and was able to refold back into its native state to a very high degree after it had been thermally unfolded. For low azidation degrees ($N_3:NH_2$ 0.2:1 to 1:1), this unfolding behavior remained unchanged, which was also confirmed by the first derivative of the recorded signals. However, for high azidation degrees, the folding behavior changed significantly ($T_m = 36.5^\circ C$, $N_3:NH_2$ 3:1) until no melting points were visible ($N_3:NH_2$ 5:1). Additionally, no refolding was observed.

The obtained nanoDSF results are in agreement with the CD spectroscopy measurements and thus confirm that the structure of ApoA1 is affected when a high number of functional groups is introduced. More specifically, the native structure of ApoA1 can be preserved up to a functionalization degree of maximum 10 azide groups per protein.

These findings highlight the importance to control the degree of protein modification to ensure their structural integrity. Otherwise, protein properties might be limited and the final targeting efficiency of the system would be dramatically affected. On the other hand, for further attachment of the protein to nanocarriers or other surfaces, only one reactive azide moiety is required for

Figure 3. A) Molar ratio of lipid membrane composition of all liposome samples. B) Physico-chemical characterization of liposome samples regarding size, obtained by dynamic light scattering at a scattering angle of 90° , zeta potential, measured in 0.1 mM KCl solution, and number of accessible amino groups, analyzed via fluorescamine assay.

successful coupling, but this might decrease the overall reaction probability. Thus, it is necessary to reach a compromise in which the protein exhibits the lowest azidation degree and maintains high functionality.

2.2. Liposome Preparation and Characterization

To further develop and optimize the ApoA1 modification strategy, liposomes were used as important representative nanocarriers. Thus, to provide different amino groups to the liposome formulations for further functionalization, three different liposome compositions of 5%, 15% and 33% of 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE), together with eggPC and cholesterol were used for the preparation of liposomes (Figure 3A) via lipid film hydration followed by extrusion method. The original lipid concentration before extrusion was adjusted to 5 mg mL^{-1} and dispersed in PBS buffer in order to maintain the physiological environment of the sample. Before the surface modification, the physico-chemical properties of the liposome samples were characterized in detail. Thus, for size and surface charge characterization of the samples, dynamic light scattering and zeta potential measurements were performed, respectively. The zeta potential data showed a moderate negative charge for the three liposome compositions due to the fact that the DOPE head group is negatively charged at neutral pH. Thus, accordingly a decrease in the zeta potential with increasing DOPE content in the liposome formulations could be observed. Importantly, DOPE content did not affect the final liposome size, since the membrane composition gives enough flexibility to be efficiently extruded through the membrane of 200 nm pore size, obtaining hydrodynamic diameters close to that value. The final synthesized liposomes were obtained with a solid content of $\approx 0.35 \text{ wt\%}$ (3.5 mg mL^{-1}). Furthermore, the number of accessible amino groups was also de-

termined by a fluorescamine assay,^[15] which is of key importance to define the conditions for subsequent functionalization of the liposome surface. According to the assay, an increase in the number of amino groups while increasing the DOPE content in the lipid membrane was observed. The obtained characterization parameters are summarized in the table of Figure 3B. Liposome size distributions are given in Figure S2 (Supporting Information).

2.3. Conjugation of DBCO Groups to Liposomes Via NHS Ester Reaction

For the functionalization of liposomes, the introduction of alkyne groups is needed to perform a further click chemistry reaction with the previously azidated ApoA1. Thus, DBCO-PEG₄-NHS ester was used, since it specifically reacts with the primary amine groups on the liposomes' surface, which are introduced by the DOPE lipid molecules. Therefore, this strategy could also be applied to other carrier systems, with the only requirement being the presence of accessible amino groups in their structure.

The reaction of NHS ester with amines is pH-dependent, and its efficiency between pH 7.1 – 8.2 was previously confirmed by our group.^[8] Therefore, the reaction was carried out in PBS (pH 7.4) to ensure physiological environment and to preserve the stability of human proteins. In order to evaluate the efficiency of the DBCO conjugation on the liposomes, different molar DBCO:NH₂ ratios were used for the reaction (1:1, 3:1 and 6:1) with three different liposome formulations.

For quantification of the number of DBCO groups, an anthracene azide assay was performed.^[19] The assay is based on a click reaction of Anth-N₃ (9-(azidomethyl) anthracene) to the DBCO-modified liposomes. Afterwards, the fluorescence of Anth-N₃ (Ex: 370 nm, Em: 414 nm) was recorded and subsequently the number of DBCO groups per liposomes was calculated (Figure 4). For the 5% DOPE liposome composition, the NH₂ group number was relatively low and therefore, saturation of DBCO groups was reached for all DBCO:NH₂ ratios to

Figure 4. Quantification of DBCO groups on the liposome's surface via anthracene-azide assay of different DBCO:NH₂ ratios as a function of the DOPE content in the liposome membrane.

almost the same DBCO groups per liposome as the initial number of amino groups. Increasing the amount of DOPE to 15%, the NH_2 group number on the liposome surface was higher, thus the saturation of DBCO groups was not reached. For the three DBCO: NH_2 ratios, the number of DBCO groups was lower than the initial number of amino groups in the control sample. However, a linear dependence was observed when increasing the amount of available DBCO linker for reaction. Finally, for the 33% DOPE formulation, the number of NH_2 groups per liposome may have led to steric hindrance and the inhibition of a similarly high conversion to DBCO groups. As a result, the proportion of DBCO per NH_2 groups obtained was lower than in the case of 15% DOPE and the linear dependence when increasing the DBCO proportion was no longer observed.

From the results, DBCO coupling efficiency is strongly dependent on the amino group content of the lipid membrane formulation. This behavior might in turn affect the efficiency of subsequent click reactions with a corresponding targeting agent, which is the previously azidated ApoA1 in this study.

2.4. Apolipoprotein Coupling to Liposomes Via Copper-Free Click Reaction

To conduct the final click reaction between liposomes and ApoA1, a fixed molar ratio of DBCO: NH_2 3:1 was selected as a compromise, given previous observations that DBCO coupling reaches a good reaction efficiency at this ratio without the aggregation effect observed at higher ratios. The DBCO-functionalized liposomes were incubated with the azide-modified ApoA1 proteins overnight at room temperature. Using the strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition (SpAAC), the azide-modified ApoA1 proteins were covalently immobilized on the DBCO-functionalized liposomes' surface. For the evaluation of the reaction, three different reaction conditions (ratio between DBCO groups to ApoA1 proteins 500:1, 100:1, and 50:1) with an azide to NH_2 reaction ratio of 0.2:1 (corresponding to 1–4 azide groups per ApoA1 protein, see Figure 1B) were investigated. This azidation degree was selected because it maintains the native structure of the protein and provides the minimum number of azide groups required for reaction. The size and size distribution of final constructs were measured by DLS (see Figure S3, Supporting Information) to verify that liposome-protein conjugates were intact and without aggregation.

First, the amount of ApoA1 covalently attached to the liposomes was quantified via the Pierce 660 nm protein assay. Then, the number of ApoA1 molecules per liposome was calculated from the protein content and the liposome concentration based on the approximate ratio between the dry weight and size of liposomes.^[15] The obtained average number of ApoA1 molecules per liposome are shown in Figure 5A. As such, the obtained results exhibit a similar trend to those previously observed. For 5% of DOPE, a possible steric hindrance due to the protein dimensions may inhibit effective coupling with all DBCO groups, leading to significantly less ApoA1 groups compared to DBCO ones. Here, no significant differences were observed between the amount of ApoA1 per liposome for the three DBCO:ApoA1 ratios. However in the case of 15% of DOPE, a decrease of ApoA1 groups was observed with decreasing DBCO:ApoA1 ratios. Fi-

nally, for 33% of DOPE, the DBCO concentration and ApoA1 amount may both be too high to exhibit any reasonable tendency. Thus, for further experiments on the effect of coupling, the liposome formulation of 15% DOPE was selected.

To verify that ApoA1 was indeed bound to the liposomes and could still be recognized by secondary antibodies, flow cytometry measurements were carried out using our previously established protocol.^[20] For this purpose, a fluorescently-labeled monoclonal antibody (Alexa Fluor 647, rabbit anti-human ApoA1, clone 2083D), which selectively binds to the immobilized human ApoA1 proteins on the liposomes' surface, was utilized. Liposomes without ApoA1 on the surface were incubated with the anti-human ApoA1 antibody as a control for the detection of the adsorption signal. The obtained fraction of fluorescence-positive liposomes together with the corresponding median fluorescence intensities (MFI) are shown in Figure 5B,C.

According to the flow cytometry analysis, a high percentage of the Alexa Fluor 647-fluorescence positive liposomes were detected for all Lipo-DBCO:ApoA1 ratios ($\approx 43\%$ to $\approx 51\%$), which seemed to increase with the amount of ApoA1 used for the surface modification. However, this increase was not statistically significant. In contrast, the control ("Lipo") showed almost no unspecific adsorption of the Alexa Fluor 647 antibody ($<1\%$, Figure 5B). The fact that not all liposomes were detected to be positive for Alexa Fluor 647 might be related to the inherent size limit of the flow cytometry detection (≈ 200 nm).^[21] Of course, it could also be due to inhomogeneous distribution of ApoA1, but it seems rather unlikely that some liposomes are fully covered while others are not functionalized at all. In addition, the MFI for Alexa Fluor 647-positive liposomes (Figure 5C) was significantly higher compared to the control and similar for all Lipo-DBCO:ApoA1 ratios. These results complement the data obtained by the protein assay, suggesting that effective functionalization with ApoA1 and effective antibody recognition of ApoA1 can both be achieved at low functional surface group concentrations.

2.5. Evaluation of ApoA1-Functionalized Liposomes Cellular Uptake

To further investigate and verify the biological activity of the ApoA1-modified liposomes, which is closely related to the structural integrity of ApoA1, we analyzed their behavior in a murine macrophage cell line (RAW264.7, DSMZ, Germany). We chose RAW264.7 as a cell line because they have been demonstrated to internalize human ApoA1.^[22] Therefore, ApoA1-modified liposomes were expected to show increased uptake in the RAW cells in contrast to pristine liposomes.

For this investigation, ApoA1 proteins with either 1–4 or 3–6 azides per molecule were covalently bound to the DBCO-functionalized liposomes with different Lipo-DBCO to ApoA1 protein ratios (100:1 and 50:1 for 1–4 azides per ApoA1 protein as well as 500:1 and 100:1 for 3–6 azides per ApoA1 protein). These different ApoA1 decorated liposomes were then tested in the RAW macrophage cell uptake (Figure 6). For the cell uptake, 1.5×10^5 cells mL^{-1} were incubated with two different concentrations (75 and 150 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of the liposomes in cell culture medium (DMEM) with and without 10% fetal bovine serum

Figure 5. Verification of the presence of ApoA1 on the liposomal surface. Previous azidation of ApoA1 was carried out with 1–4 azide groups per ApoA1. A) ApoA1 quantification for liposomes modified with human ApoA1 proteins via Pierce 660 nm assay. B) and C) flow cytometry measurements. The ApoA1 decorated liposomes were incubated with a secondary AF647-labeled anti-human ApoA1 antibody (clone 2083D) for 30 min at 4 °C. Different reaction conditions (ratio between DBCO groups to ApoA1 proteins 500:1, 100:1, and 50:1) were analyzed. Unmodified liposomes were applied as a negative control. The fraction of AF647-positive liposomes in % B) and the median fluorescence intensity (MFI) in arbitrary units (a. u.) is shown C).

(FBS, ThermoFisher). The presence of additional serum proteins in the medium leads to the formation of a biomolecular corona around the liposomal surface, which is more representative of a physiological environment.^[23] In contrast to the unmodified liposomes, the ApoA1 functionalized liposomes showed an increase in uptake by the RAW cells for each condition. The observed uptake was concentration-dependent (75 and 150 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Moreover, the uptake was influenced by the amount of ApoA1 on the liposome surface (100:1 and 50:1) with more protein leading to a slight increase in cellular uptake. Additional serum proteins in the medium that generated the biomolecular corona around the surface further led to a slightly lower uptake (orange bars). Thus, the associated corona proteins may have masked the attached ApoA1 or exerted an inhibition effect on cellular uptake and thus outcompeted with the targeting group. However, the differences observed with and without FBS were slight, especially at the lower concentration. The effect of the corona was more pronounced at the higher concentration, however, the uptake was still significantly higher compared to pristine liposomes. Thus, ApoA1 remains biologically active despite the presence of the biomolecular

corona. For the Lipo-DBCO:ApoA1 ratio of 500:1 at 75 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in medium containing serum proteins, a non-concentration dependent uptake behavior was observed (75 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ vs 150 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, orange bars). The reason for this is not clear, although it might be related to the fact that this was the sample with lowest ApoA1 coverage. In this case, the corona formed in FBS may have been more influential compared to the low ApoA1 density. Interestingly, in all other cases, cell uptake was not influenced by the azidation degree or the protein amount. This suggests that the optimal coupling conditions should incorporate the lowest azidation degree possible to limit its influence on structure, yet high enough to maintain sufficient surface coverage of targeting groups.

Taken together, the results indicate that the native structure of ApoA1 was retained during functionalization and, thus, a cellular response could be achieved. Indeed, the structure of ApoA1 has been shown to affect the cholesterol removal of nascent discoidal HDL particles by RAW cells.^[24] This underlines the importance of maintaining the structural integrity and associated effects of not only ApoA1 but other potential targeting proteins. However,

Figure 6. ApoA1 decorated liposomes favor a cellular uptake by macrophages. The liposomal cell uptake in the murine macrophage cell line RAW264.7 is shown. The cell uptake was conducted with a sample concentration of 75 or 150 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in medium without (blue bars) or with 10% FBS (orange bars) for 2 h at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 . Only viable cells were gated and analyzed by flow cytometry. Values are given as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). MFI [a.u.] = median fluorescence intensity [arbitrary units].

it is important to mention that for final targeting applications in specific tissues/cell types, receptor recognition needs to be validated, e.g. by receptor-blocking experiments. Overall, our presented functionalization strategy is suitable for conjugation of various different protein types with precise characterization of each reaction step and the possibility to adjust for the optimal functionalization degrees before diving into biological testing.

3. Conclusion

In this work, we developed a minimal functionalization strategy of proteins that maintains their structural stability and functionality. ApoA1 was chosen as the representative protein to be chemically modified with an azide-PEG linker via NHS ester chemistry. The reaction was monitored by MALDI-ToF, showing that the mass increase of the protein is proportional to the number of used azide linkers. On the other hand, protein stability was evaluated by analyzing the secondary structure using CD spectroscopy and the corresponding melting/denaturation point by nanoDSF. It was confirmed that ApoA1 structure is affected when a high number of azide linkers are introduced, 10 being the maximum number of functional groups that can be coupled to the protein without loss of the secondary structure. Furthermore, the chemically modified ApoA1 was used for coupling to liposomes as nanocarrier systems. Liposome samples were first obtained by lipid film rehydration followed by extrusion method and second modified with a strained alkyne via NHS ester chemistry. This way, a subsequent SPAAC click chemistry reaction between the azidated-ApoA1 and alkyne-functionalized liposomes was carried out. The coupling of the ApoA1 to the liposomes was evaluated by flow cytometry analysis, confirming the effective functionalization of liposomes with minimally modified ApoA1 and at the same time that ApoA1 can still be recognized

by specific antibodies. Furthermore, cellular internalization of ApoA1-functionalized liposomes in macrophages confirmed that the coupled ApoA1 indeed leads to a cellular response. The developed minimal protein modification procedure could be easily applied to other proteins for attachment to different surfaces or nanocarriers while maintaining protein functionality. As such, this finding could open the door for the design of more efficient nanocarrier systems.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: All chemicals were used as received. Human Apolipoprotein A1 (ApoA1, purity > 99%) was purchased from MyBioSource (USA). The azide 15-Azido-4,7,10,13-tetraoxa-pentadecanoic acid succinimidyl ester (N3-PEG4-NHS) was procured from Jena Bioscience GmbH (Germany). 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE, purity \geq 99%), L- α -phosphatidylcholine (egg PC, purity \geq 99%), cholesterol (Chol, purity \geq 99%) and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, purity > 99%) were purchased from Merck (Germany). Fluorescamine (purity \geq 98%) was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. The dye Dil Stain (1,1'-Diocetadecyl-3,3',3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine perchlorate) for labelling liposomes was purchased from Merck (Germany). Dibenzylcyclooctyne (DBCO)-PEG₄-NHS was purchased from Thermo Fisher (Germany). Phosphate buffered saline (DPBS-buffer, $-\text{Mg}^{2+}$, $-\text{Ca}^{2+}$) was obtained from Merck (Germany), while ethanol (99.5%) was acquired from Carl Roth, Germany. A MilliQ device (Merck Millipore, Germany) was used to obtain demineralized water, which was applied in all experiments. The macrophage cell line was bought from Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen GmbH (DSMZ), Germany.

Azidation of ApoA1 Via NHS Ester Reaction: For the reaction, ApoA1 concentration was adjusted to 1 mg mL^{-1} in PBS. Each ApoA1 protein contains 23 reactive amino groups (22 lysines + N-terminus). In this work, different molar ratios between NHS-PEG₄-N₃ per NH₂ groups were used: 0.2:1, 0.4:1, 0.8:1, 1:1, 3:1, and 5:1. Thus, the corresponding aliquots of NHS-PEG₄-N₃ (stock solution 10 mM in DMSO) were mixed together with 1 mL of ApoA1 to reach the abovementioned N₃:NH₂ ratios. Then, the mixtures were stirred at 700 rpm for 2 h at room temperature. Afterward, the azidated protein was purified by Zeba columns 7 kDa molecular weight cutoff (Thermo Fisher, Germany).

Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-ToF): For the quantification of the number of NHS-PEG₄-N₃ molecules attached to each ApoA1 protein, MALDI-ToF technique was performed on a rapifleXTM MALDI-ToF/ToF mass spectrometer from Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Germany. The spectrometer is equipped with a scanning smartbeam 10 KHz Nd:YAG laser at a wavelength of 355 nm and a 10 bit 5 GHz digitizer. For each measurement 10 μL of sample was prepared in water using a sinapinic acid matrix. Data processing was carried out with mMass software.

Circular Dichroism Spectroscopy (CD spectroscopy): CD spectroscopy was used to check the secondary structure of ApoA1 after azidation. Thus, CD spectra were recorded between 180 and 260 nm on a JASCO J-1500 spectrometer in a 1 mm high precision cell. Samples were diluted to 0.05 mg mL^{-1} in water to a volume of 200 μL .

Nano Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (nanoDSF): The melting point (T_M) of ApoA1 after azidation was determined by nanoDSF measurements. A Prometheus NT.48 instrument from NanoTemper Technologies GmbH (Munich, Germany) was used together with highly sensitive glass capillaries, following the previously optimized experimental conditions.^[8] A protein concentration of 0.5 mg mL^{-1} was chosen for the measurements.

Functionalization of Azide-Modified ApoA1 with DBCO-PEG₅ kDa: The DBCO-PEG₅ kDa (2.5 mg mL^{-1} in DMSO, 1 μL , Irish Biotech GmbH, Germany) linker was further attached to the functionalized ApoA1 (0.5 mg mL^{-1} , 5 μL) by overnight incubation at room temperature. The resulting PEGylated ApoA1 conjugate was further applied to SDS-PAGE.

SDS-PAGE: ApoA1 solution was mixed with reducing agent and sample buffer and subsequently loaded onto a NuPAGE Novex 10% bis-tris gel.^[8] Protein bands were visualized with the SilverQuest Silver Staining Kit according to manufacturers' instruction (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA).

Liposome Preparation: By thin film hydration followed by extrusion, different liposome formulations were prepared. The corresponding mini extruder, polycarbonate membranes and interchangeable 1 mL syringes were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids. Following previously reported experimental conditions,^[15] three liposome samples were prepared from cholesterol (Chol), L- α -phosphatidylcholine (egg PC) and 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE) with molar compositions of 5%, 15% and 33% of DOPE. Stock solutions of the three components were prepared in chloroform at a concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹ (1.3 mm eggPC, 1.3 mm DOPE, and 2.6 mm Chol) and the labeling dye Dil at a concentration of 2 mg mL⁻¹ in DMSO. The liposome formulations were then obtained by mixing the appropriate amounts of the lipid solutions: 1) 1.44 mL eggPC, 120 μ L DOPE and 440 μ L Chol for 5% DOPE molar composition, 2) 1.44 mL eggPC, 360 μ L DOPE and 200 μ L Chol for 15% DOPE and 3) 835 μ L eggPC, 767 μ L DOPE, and 398 μ L Chol for 33% DOPE. After evaporation of the organic solvent the lipid films were hydrated with PBS and extruded as described previously, leading to the production of dispersions of small unilamellar liposomes.

Liposome Characterization—Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): DLS measurements were performed with diluted dispersions^[8] with a Zetasizer Nano S90 (Malvern Panalytical GmbH, Germany) at 20 °C.

Liposome Characterization—Zeta Potential: For zeta-potential (ζ -potential) characterization of the liposome samples, diluted with 1 mM KCl,^[8] a Zetasizer Nano Z (Malvern Panalytical GmbH, Germany) with disposable folded capillary cells was used.

Liposome Characterization—Quantification of Primary Amine Groups on the Surface of Liposomes: For the quantification of the amino groups available on the liposome surface, a fluorescamine assay (FA assay) was carried out.^[8] Hexylamine was used to obtain a standard calibration curve. The corresponding fluorescence emission (Ex: 410, Em: 470 nm) was detected in a plate reader (Tecan AG, Switzerland) immediately after mixing aliquots of freshly prepared fluorescamine solution (0.3 mg mL⁻¹ in acetone), together with the samples and borate buffer (0.1 M, pH = 9.5).

Conjugation of DBCO Groups to Liposomes Via NHS Ester Reaction: A stock solution of DBCO-PEG₄-NHS ester ($M_w = 388.37$ g mol⁻¹) was prepared at a concentration of 40 mg mL⁻¹ in dry DMSO. Then, the molar ratio of DBCO molecules to surface available amino groups in the liposomes was varied to be 1:1, 3:1 and 6:1. Thus, 126 μ L, 63 μ L or 21 μ L of DBCO stock solution were added to 500 μ L liposome sample (3.5 mg mL⁻¹). The mixtures were vortexed for 20 s and the NHS ester conjugation reactions were then carried out by stirring at 700 rpm over night at room temperature. Afterwards, liposomes were purified by centrifugation 3x (20 000 g, 4 °C, 1 h) and redispersed in PBS.

Quantification of the DBCO Groups on the Liposomes' Surface: To determine the DBCO conjugation efficiency, an anthracene-azide (Anth-N₃) assay was carried out. Aliquots of freshly prepared Anth-N₃ stock solution (1.7 mg mL⁻¹ in dry DMSO) were mixed with the DBCO-modified liposomes (≈ 3.5 mg mL⁻¹) in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and vortexed for 20 s: (a-b) 17.3 μ L Anth-N₃/32.6 μ L DMSO; (c-d) 25 μ L liposome dispersion/17.5 μ L Anth-N₃/7.63 μ L DMSO; (e) 25 μ L liposome dispersion/25 μ L DMSO. All mixtures were placed on a shaking box protected from light over night at 25 °C. Afterwards, the samples were diluted 10 and 100 times by DMSO and the fluorescence was measured by a plate reader (Ex: 370 nm, Em: 414 nm). The measurement data were calculated according to a previously reported procedure.^[25]

Liposome Surface Functionalization with ApoA1 Via Copper-Free Click Chemistry: For click chemistry reaction liposomes of 15% DOPE were used. A volume of 400 μ L of DBCO-modified liposomes (≈ 3.5 mg mL⁻¹ in PBS) were used for click chemistry reaction with different amounts of azidated-ApoA1 (0.6 mg mL⁻¹ in PBS). Thus, 50 μ L, 25 μ L and 5 μ L of ApoA1-N₃ were added to the DBCO-liposomes to reach DBCO:ApoA1 ratios of 50:1, 100:1 and 500:1, respectively. The mixtures were stirred at

500 rpm for two days at room temperature. Afterward, samples were purified by centrifugation at 20 000 g, 4 °C, 30 min and redispersed in PBS.

Protein Quantification: To quantify the ApoA1 concentration successfully attached to the liposomes, the Pierce 660 nm Protein Assay Reagent with Ionic Detergent Compatibility Reagent (Thermo Scientific, Germany) was used following the manufacturer's instructions. Freshly prepared bovine serum albumin solutions (Sigma Aldrich, Germany) were used to perform a standard calibration curve. The absorption was measured at 660 nm in a plate reader (Tecan AG, Switzerland) at 25 °C in triplicate.

Culturing of Macrophage Cells: The murine RAW264.7 macrophage cell line (DSMZ, Germany) was cultured in Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% penicillin (100 U mL⁻¹), streptomycin (100 mg mL⁻¹), and 2 mM glutamine in a TC 75 cm² flask (Greiner, Germany). The cells were cultivated in an incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ humidity (CO₂ Incubator C200, Labotect), following the protocol previously reported.^[26] The confluence of the cells was routinely checked under the microscope. When a confluence greater than or equal to 80% was reached, the cells were passaged. The consumed media was discarded, and the cells were briefly washed with 10 mL PBS (Merck, Germany). For the detachment of the cells, 10 mL of trypsin-EDTA (Thermo, Germany) was added and the cells were incubated for 10 min at 37 °C. Following detachment, 10 mL of FBS containing DMEM medium was added. The resulting cell suspensions were transferred into a 50 mL tube and centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min. The supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was resuspended in 10–20 mL of the respective FBS containing medium. The cell viability was checked with trypan blue, by mixing 20 μ L of cell suspension to 20 μ L of Trypan Blue Solution (Merck, Germany) of which 10 μ L were pipetted onto a counting slide and the live count was measured by an automated cell counter (TC10, Bio-Rad). Dependent on the live count, the cell suspension was used for experimental procedures or for keeping the cells in culture.

Fluorescence Calibration of Liposomal Formulations: Based on the solid content of the liposomal formulations, the fluorescence of each sample was investigated with the Infinite M1000 plate reader (Tecan). For this purpose, 5 μ L of the liposomes were added to 95 μ L PBS and transferred into a black 96 well microplate (Greiner Bio-One, Germany). The fluorescence emission of the sample (stained with Dil dye) was detected (Ex: 550 nm, Em: 567 nm). Based on the solid content of the pristine liposomes, each of the relative fluorescent units (RFUs) were correlated. Thereby, differences in the fluorescence intensities were equalized, which was important for the detection of the fluorescence by flow cytometry.

Cell Uptake Experiments: For the cell uptake experiments, 1.5×10^5 cells mL⁻¹ were seeded per well in a 24-well plate and left to attach overnight in a humidified incubator at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.^[26] The next day, the FBS-containing medium was exchanged to medium without FBS (≈ 90 min) so that the cells could adapt to the serum-free environment. The same procedure was carried out for FBS-containing medium. All samples were prepared in triplicates and incubated for 2 h with a concentration of 75 or 150 μ g mL⁻¹ (pristine or ApoA1 decorated liposomes) in 250 μ L of medium (with or without FBS) per well. Afterwards, the cells were washed with 1 mL PBS. Cell detachment was performed with 250 μ L of Trypsin-EDTA for 10 min at 37 °C. Afterwards, the cells were separated from the wells by adding 250 μ L of FBS-containing medium. The cell suspension was transferred into a 1.5 mL micro tube and centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min. Zombie Aqua (Biolegend) was used as a live versus dead assay. For this, two out of the three samples were incubated with the Zombie Aqua dye (1:500, in 100 μ L PBS) for 15 min at 4 °C in the dark. The control samples were incubated with PBS. After the incubation, the cells were centrifuged at 300 g for 5 min and the supernatant was discarded. Finally, the cell pellet was resuspended in 1 mL PBS and analyzed by flow cytometry.

Flow Cytometry: Flow cytometry was used to quantify the liposomal formulations that were taken up by or attached to the cells. The fluorescence-labeled liposomal formulations (Dil dye with 550/567 nm) were detected by the YL1 channel with an excitation laser of 561 nm and a 585/16 nm band pass filter for emission. Data analysis was performed by applying Attune NxT Software. In this software, the cell population was selected with a FSC/SSC scatter plot, excluding cell debris populations. In all experiments, 10000 events were set. This selected population was

further gated based on the viable cells (Zombie Aqua) that were detected by the VL2 channel with an excitation laser of 405 nm and a 512/25 nm band pass filter for emission. The gated events of the cells were evaluated by the fluorescent signal expressed as the median fluorescence intensity (MFI).

The validation of covalently-bound human ApoA1 on the liposomal surface was analyzed by using a secondary AF647-labeled anti-human ApoA1 antibody (clone 2083D, Novus Biologicals, Germany). For this purpose, the ApoA1 decorated liposomes (2 µg) were incubated with the secondary antibody (1 µg) for 30 min at 4 °C in the dark in a total volume of 20 µL PBS. After the incubation, 1 mL of PBS was added and analyzed by flow cytometry. Like before, the liposome population was selected with an FSC/SSC scatter plot of which the Dil fluorescence was gated with a YL1/SSC plot. From this plot, the fluorescence of the secondary antibody was gated with the RL1 channel with an excitation laser of 638 nm and a 670/14 nm band pass filter for emission. Liposomes without immobilized ApoA1 on the surface were used as a negative control and in combination with the secondary antibody as a positive control. The gated events of the liposomes were evaluated by the fluorescent signal expressed as the median fluorescence intensity (MFI) and as the percentage of gated AF647-positive liposomes.

Statistical Analysis: All measurements were performed in triplicate. Therefore, the data are presented as the corresponding mean values and standard deviations.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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apolipoprotein, liposomes, nanocarriers, protein functionalization

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- [1] a) A. G. A. Sá, Y. M. F. Moreno, B. A. M. Carciofi, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* **2020**, *60*, 3367; b) J. Puetz, F. M. Wurm, *Processes* **2019**, *7*, 476; c) M. Hadidi, C. Tan, E. Assadpour, M. S. Kharazmi, S. M. Jafari, *J. Controlled Release* **2023**, *355*, 327.

- [2] J. Kalia, T. R. Raines, *Curr. Org. Chem.* **2010**, *14*, 138.
 [3] C. B. Rosen, M. B. Francis, *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **2017**, *13*, 697.
 [4] N. H. Fischer, M. T. Oliveira, F. Diness, *Biomater. Sci.* **2023**, *11*, 719.
 [5] L. Taiariol, C. Chaix, C. Farre, E. Moreau, *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 340.
 [6] Q. Wang, T. R. Chan, R. Hilgraf, V. V. Fokin, K. B. Sharpless, M. G. Finn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, *125*, 3192.
 [7] J. C. Jewett, C. R. Bertozzi, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2010**, *39*, 1272.
 [8] M. Gai, J. Simon, I. Lieberwirth, V. Mailänder, S. Morsbach, K. Landfester, *Polym. Chem.* **2020**, *11*, 527.
 [9] G. R. Bayly, in *Clinical Biochemistry: Metabolic and Clinical Aspects*, (Third Edition), (Eds.: W. J. Marshall, M. Lapsley, A. P. Day, R. M. Ayling), Churchill Livingstone, London **2014**.
 [10] M. C. Phillips, *J. Lipid Res.* **2013**, *54*, 2034.
 [11] S. Schöttler, G. Becker, S. Winzen, T. Steinbach, K. Mohr, K. Landfester, V. Mailänder, F. R. Wurm, *Nat Nano* **2016**, *11*, 372.
 [12] a) F. Re, I. Cambianica, C. Zona, S. Sesana, M. Gregori, R. Rigolio, B. L. Ferla, F. Nicotra, G. Forloni, A. Cagnotto, M. Salmona, M. Masserini, G. Sancini, *Nanomedicine* **2011**, *7*, 551; b) A. Zensi, D. Begley, C. Pontikis, C. Legros, L. Mihoreanu, C. Büchel, J. Kreuter, *J. Drug Targeting* **2010**, *18*, 842; c) B. V. Zlokovic, C. L. Martel, E. Matsubara, J. G. McComb, G. Zheng, R. T. McCluskey, B. Frangione, J. Ghiso, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **1996**, *93*, 4229; d) A. L. Zhou, S. K. Swaminathan, G. L. Curran, J. F. Poduslo, V. J. Lowe, L. Li, K. K. Kandimalla, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* **2019**, *369*, 481.
 [13] a) A. Akbarzadeh, R. Rezaei-Sadabady, S. Davaran, S. W. Joo, N. Zarghami, Y. Hanifepour, M. Samiei, M. Kouhi, K. Nejati-Koshki, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **2013**, *8*, 102; b) D. J. A. Crommelin, P. van Hoogevest, G. Storm, *J. Controlled Release* **2020**, *318*, 256.
 [14] a) V. Makwana, J. Karanjia, T. Haselhorst, S. Anoopkumar-Dukie, S. Rudrawar, *Int. J. Pharm.* **2021**, *593*, 120117; b) A. Mateos-Maroto, J. E. F. Rubio, S. Prévost, A. Maestro, R. G. Rubio, F. Ortega, E. Guzmán, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2023**, *640*, 220.
 [15] A. Mateos-Maroto, M. Gai, M. Brückner, R. daCosta Marques, I. Harley, J. Simon, V. Mailänder, S. Morsbach, K. Landfester, *Acta Biomater.* **2023**, *158*, 463.
 [16] S. Schöttler, G. Becker, S. Winzen, T. Steinbach, K. Mohr, K. Landfester, V. Mailänder, F. R. Wurm, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2016**, *11*, 372.
 [17] J. Rip, G. J. Schenk, A. G. de Boer, *Expert Opin. Drug Delivery* **2009**, *6*, 227.
 [18] L. Z. Huang, K. L. Chambliss, X. F. Gao, I. S. Yuhanna, E. Behling-Kelly, S. Bergaya, M. Ahmed, P. Michaely, K. Luby-Phelps, A. Darehshouri, L. Xu, E. A. Fisher, W. P. Ge, C. Mineo, P. W. Shaul, *Nature* **2019**, *569*, 565.
 [19] G. Baier, J. M. Siebert, K. Landfester, A. Musyanovych, *Macromolecules* **2012**, *45*, 3419.
 [20] M. Tonigold, J. Simon, D. Estupiñán, M. Kokkinopoulou, J. Reinholz, U. Kintzel, A. Kaltbeitzel, P. Renz, M. P. Domogalla, K. Steinbrink, I. Lieberwirth, D. Crespy, K. Landfester, V. Mailänder, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2018**, *13*, 862.
 [21] E. Van Der Pol, M. J. C. Van Gemert, A. Sturk, R. Nieuwland, T. G. Van Leeuwen, *J. Thromb Haemost* **2012**, *10*, 919.
 [22] I. Lorenzi, A. von Eckardstein, C. Cavelier, S. Radosavljevic, L. Rohrer, *J. Mol Med (Berl)* **2008**, *86*, 171.
 [23] M. P. Monopoli, C. Aberg, A. Salvati, K. A. Dawson, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2012**, *7*, 779.
 [24] L. Á. Cuellar, E. D. Prieto, L. V. Cabaleiro, H. A. Garda, *Biochim Biophys Acta* **2014**, *1841*, 180.
 [25] S. F. M. van Dongen, M. Nallani, S. Schoffelen, J. J. L. M. Cornelissen, R. J. M. Nolte, J. C. M. van Hest, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2008**, *29*, 321.
 [26] M. Brückner, J. Simon, K. Landfester, V. Mailänder, *Nanoscale* **2021**, *13*, 9816.